

PATHOMORPHOLOGY CHANGES IN TOXIC KIDNEY DAMAGE AND THE EFFECT OF LEONTOZIDE DRUG ON IT

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Annotation: The toxic effect of tetrachloromethane, which leads to pathomorphofunctional changes in the whole organism, is being studied by foreign and domestic scientists. Tetrachloromethane enters the body through the skin, lungs and mouth. It is proven that it spreads throughout the body through the blood and causes histomorphological changes in the liver, kidneys, lungs and other vital organs.

Today, the development of the chemical industry has a positive effect on the increase in the number of toxic nephrosis, which significantly contributes to the formation of occupational diseases. In this case, along with the kidneys, other organs are also damaged. Liver and kidney damage is dominant. Sometimes kidney damage is accompanied by clinical, biochemical and morphological signs of acute and chronic renal failure. This disease is more common in people with 5-6 years of work experience, with an average age of 45-80 years. In addition, a high incidence rate is also observed in professions that are more in contact with tetrachloromethane (refrigerators, freezers, fire extinguishers, workers with agricultural chemicals). The above indicates that the treatment and prevention of various intoxications is an urgent problem today, and the study of the reduction of the course of intoxication processes by positively enhancing the pathomorphological and morphofunctional changes in organs and tissues that detoxify these toxins by leontoside is of great importance.

Purpose of the study. To study the morphofunctional changes caused by the cytotoxicity of CCL4 to kidney tissues under experimental conditions and to identify the specific aspects of the effect of leontoside on these morphofunctional changes.

Object and subject of the study: experiments were conducted on 75 outbred, adult, albino, male rats with an initial weight of 130-150 g. They were divided into 3 groups:

Group I was the control, 15 rats were isolated and fed in normal vivarium conditions.

Group II consisted of 30 experimental animals, divided into 7-day (10), 14-day (10), and 21-day (10) groups. Rats are injected subcutaneously once a day for 3 days with a 50% oily solution of SSI4 at a rate of 1.2 ml/100 g of body weight.

30 experimental animals were selected for group III and divided into groups of 7 days (5), 14 days (5), 21 days (5). Rats are administered 1.2 ml/100 g of oily solution of CCI4 and 0.025 mg/g of leontoside.

To study the pathomorphological, morphometric, morphofunctional changes in the kidneys of experimental animals, animals are anesthetized under ether anesthesia on the 7th, 14th and 21st days of the experiment, anesthetized and examined.

Analysis of the results: When the experimental animals (rats) were administered only carbon tetrachloride, profound and irreversible changes were observed in the kidney tissue. Histological examinations revealed the following:

Tubular apparatus: A pronounced hydropic and fatty dystrophy is detected in the epithelium of the proximal and distal tubules. Cell destruction is observed in many areas, and the lumen of the tubules is filled with desquamated epithelium and protein masses.

Glomerular apparatus: In the renal glomeruli, compression of the capillary loops and expansion of the space of the Shumlyansky-Bowman capsule are observed. Proliferation of mesangial cells and thickening of the basement membrane are detected.

Stroma and blood vessels: Interstitial edema and venous congestion are clearly visible. Lympho-macrophage infiltration develops in the interstitial space, which indicates an acute course of the inflammatory process.

Under the influence of the drug Leontozide, along with regenerative processes in the kidneys, the pathomorphological picture in the group receiving Leontozide changes significantly in a positive direction. The nephroprotective properties of this drug were manifested in the following:

Reduction in dystrophy: The degree of granular and hydropic dystrophy in the tubular epithelium is 1.5–2 times less than in the "control" group. The nuclei of the cells retain their shape, the oxyphilicity of the cytoplasm is restored. **Signs of regeneration:** In the microscopic picture, increased mitotic activity of nephrocytes and the formation of a new epithelial layer (restitution) are noticeable. This is explained by the fact that Leontozide stimulates intracellular protein synthesis. **Vascular system:** Blood circulation in the kidneys improves, stagnation in the microcirculatory basin and interstitial edema decrease.

Conclusion: A comparative analysis of the conducted experiment shows that under the influence of Leontozide, the structural integrity of the nephron, which is the morpho-functional unit of the kidney, is preserved. Leontozide not only protects cells from poisoning, but also stabilizes the excretory and filtration functions of the kidney during the pathological process.

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